

Rotational signatures of dispersive stacking in the formation of aromatic dimers

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Abstract: The aggregation of aromatic species is dictated by inter- and intramolecular forces. Not only is characterizing these forces in aromatic growth important for understanding grain formation in the interstellar medium, but it is also imperative to comprehend biological functions. We report a combined rotational spectroscopic and quantum-chemical study on three structurally related aromatic homo-dimers to analyse the influence of structural flexibility and the presence of heteroatoms on dimer formation. The dimers are comprised of diphenylether, dibenzofuran, and fluorene. The obtained structural information shows clear similarities between the dimers despite their qualitatively different molecular interactions. All dimers are dominated by dispersion interactions such as CH- π or π - π , but the dibenzofuran dimer is also influenced by repulsion between the free electron pairs of the oxygen atoms and the π clouds. This study lays the groundwork for understanding the first steps of molecular aggregation in systems with aromatic residues.

The interplay between different intermolecular forces drives (bio)molecular aggregation and recognition.^[1] Although significant theoretical and experimental progress has been made, molecular recognition based on non-covalent interactions is still not fully understood at a quantitative molecular level.^[2] Decoupling the complex balance of forces that define non-covalent interactions and understanding exactly how the various non-covalent interactions reinforce or compete with each other in complex systems is of fundamental and practical importance. The generation of a toolbox of molecular groups that can introduce specific types of intermolecular interactions into a system would help synthetic chemists shape molecules in ways that customize the interaction forces. This can be by the inclusion of specific heteroatoms such as oxygen and fluorine or bulky groups supporting dispersion. Another aspect that has yet to receive more attention is the role of structural flexibility.^[3] Further knowledge will help predict and design the outcome of molecular recognition events. A better quantitative description of dispersion interactions is one of the key steps towards this goal. In molecular chemistry, dispersion interactions are omnipresent.^[4] Protein and DNA stability and the binding mechanism between DNA-protein are in part governed by such interactions in aromatic systems.^[5] Mainly two arrangements can

arise in these structures: edge-to-face (dominated by CH- π interactions) and stacked orientations (dominated by π - π dispersion interactions). A prototypical system for studying the subtle balance between these two assemblies is the benzene dimer. It has received much experimental attention and also acts as a benchmark for quantum-chemical calculations on systems involving these intricate dispersive interactions.^[6] By using rotational spectroscopy, the rich internal dynamics of the T-shaped global minimum structure and therefore the edge-to-face cooperation between the benzene molecules of the benzene dimer were revealed.^[7]

Here, we concentrate on a comparative rotational spectroscopy study of dimers of the structurally related aromatic molecules diphenylether (DPE), dibenzofuran (DBF), and the polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbon (PAH) fluorene (FLU) (see Scheme 1). Such complexes can be important nucleation seeds for molecular clustering and its growth. Our broadband rotational spectroscopy study will provide us with important insight on the first steps of molecular aggregation, which can also be relevant for understanding the first steps of ice grain formation.^[8] This technique can provide unprecedented structural information for isolated molecules and complexes.^[9]

Scheme 1: Lewis structures of the monomers diphenylether (DPE), dibenzofuran (DBF), and the polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbon (PAH) fluorene (FLU).

Aromatic rings provide powerful dispersion centers due to their polarizable, delocalized π electron systems and their planarity, which allows for short intermolecular contacts. All three molecules consist of these extended π electron clouds that are amenable to strong π - π and CH- π intermolecular interactions. As in the case of the benzene dimer, at least two qualitatively different structures are possible: a stacking configuration mainly resulting from π - π interactions and a T-shaped structure due to CH- π interactions as well as combinations thereof.

Despite their clear similarities, DPE, DBF, and FLU differ in structural flexibility, symmetry, dipole moment magnitudes as well as the presence or absence of an oxygen atom. Their comparative study will thus allow us to pin down the influences of these properties on the preferred dimer structure. The DBF and the FLU dimers were studied before using laser spectroscopy techniques to investigate low-lying excimer states, but their structures were not unambiguously identified.^[10]

DBF is structurally related to FLU, which is a three-ring PAH with an extended π electron system. Due to its symmetry (point group C_{2v}), FLU has a permanent dipole moment calculated to be 0.56 D along the C_2 symmetry axis. For DBF, FLU's CH_2 group is exchanged for an oxygen atom, with the C_{2v} symmetry being preserved. The overall calculated dipole moment of DBF is 0.7 D

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along the C_2 symmetry axis. DPE's calculated dipole moment is 1.17 D. While FLU and DBF are planar, rigid molecules, DPE is flexible and exhibits low-barrier tunneling between equivalent minima. We thus expect that DPE can adjust its arrangement of the phenyl rings to maximize molecular interactions upon dimer formation, as we observed in a previous study on DPE-alcohol and DPE-H₂O complexes.^[3a] For those complexes, DPE's flexibility led to an, at first glance, counter-intuitive binding site preference for larger, bulky alcohols to DPE.

The rotational spectra of the three dimers were recorded with the Hamburg CP-FTMW spectrometer COMPACT in the 2-8 GHz range, and the cold and isolated conditions of a molecular jet were exploited.^[11] Experimental details are provided in the Experimental and Computational Section in the supplementary material. In the following, we summarize the rotational spectroscopy results for all three dimers and provide a comparative discussion of their structures and respective intermolecular interactions.

Sections of the experimental spectra with simulations employing the experimentally determined rotational parameters for the complexes are shown in Figure 1. For the DPE dimer ($C_{24}O_2H_{20}$, molecular mass 340 amu), the experimental rotational constants are summarized in Table 1 together with calculated values for two dimer structures from quantum chemistry. Only one dimer species is observed in the experiment (Figure 2a), and there is no indication of further dimer spectra. Quantum-chemical calculations predict two low-lying forms, with an energy difference of only 0.9 kJ/mol. Three further dimers are predicted to be 5.7, 9.0, and 15.9 kJ/mol higher in energy, which are too high in energy to be sufficiently populated under the cold conditions of our molecular jet (Figure S1). The two low-energy dimers, however, are structurally very similar, resulting in similar rotational constants. They differ in the relative orientation of one phenyl group: Dimer 1 has the CH- π interaction in the C2 (ortho) hydrogen while for dimer 2 the C3 (meta) hydrogen is involved in this interaction (Figure S1).

It is not possible to unambiguously assign the experimentally observed dimer to either the calculated dimer 1 or to dimer 2. Both dimers should be populated under the cold conditions of the molecular jet. The experimental rotational constants are closer to the ones calculated for dimer 2, while the large number of assigned c-type transitions points to dimer 1 (Table 1). The observance of only one dimer could point towards a low relaxation barrier between them. Re-optimization at the MP2/aug-cc-pVTZ level led to a larger energy difference of about 4.8 kJ/mol (not ZPE corrected, with dimer 2 higher in energy).

As mentioned, the main intermolecular interaction is CH- π , with some additional CH-O interactions (Figure 2a), which also expresses itself in the larger electrostatic contribution to the

binding energy compared to the other two dimers (DBF and FLU) based on a symmetry-adapted perturbation theory (SAPT) analysis (see below, Table 4). The shortest CH-O distances in the DPE dimer are 3.2 Å. While we observe rich internal dynamics for the DPE monomer, these are quenched upon dimer formation. In this respect it is also interesting to compare the dihedral angles ψ_1 and ψ_2 (defined in Figure S2) in the two DPE molecules (DPE1 and DPE2, Figure S3) to those obtained in the free monomer ($\psi_1 = \psi_2 = 37.0^\circ$) and other DPE complexes. The structural flexibility of DPE allows it to rearrange for optimal interactions. In the dimer 1, $\psi_1 \approx 20^\circ$ and $\psi_2 \approx 85^\circ$ for DPE1 and $\psi_1 \approx 19^\circ$ and $\psi_2 \approx 53^\circ$ for DPE2. In the recent study on DPE complexed with water, methanol, tertbutyl alcohol, and adamantol, we found similar values for the dihedral angles of these complexes.^[3a] A comparison of the dihedral angles for the DPE dimer compared to those of the other DPE complexes is given in Table S1.

Table 1. Comparison of experimental and calculated molecular parameters of the DPE dimer. The experimental values are determined from a fit to an asymmetric rotor Hamiltonian using the SPFIT software. The calculations were performed at the B3LYP-D3(BJ)/def2TZVP level of theory.

Parameters	Experiment	Calculations Dimer 1	Calculations Dimer 2
DPE dimer			
A (MHz)	227.168244(52)	227	223
B (MHz)	179.225983(25)	205	190
C (MHz)	172.344790(25)	188	184
Δ_J (kHz)	0.019927(41)		
Δ_{JK} (kHz)	-0.01720(18)		
Δ_K (kHz)	0.01101(31)		
δ_J (kHz)	0.000713(22)		
δ_K (kHz)	-0.00900(77)		
$\mu_a/\mu_b/\mu_c$ (D)		0.8/0.9/0.5	0.9/0.9/0.1
ΔE (kJ/mol)		0	0.9
σ (kHz)	4.56		
$N_{lines}^{[b]}$ (a b c)	729 (409 186 132)		

^[a] A, B, and C are the rotational constants, Δ_J , Δ_{JK} , Δ_K , δ_J and δ_K are the experimental centrifugal distortion constants, and σ is the standard deviation of the fit.

^[b] Total number of rotational transitions included in the fit.

Figure 1. Portions of the broadband rotational spectra showing rotational signatures of the three dimers, (a) and (b) DPE, (c) DBF and (d) FLU, respectively. In each case, the black trace is the experimental spectrum, while the lower trace represents a simulation of the observed dimer (at 1 K) based on fitted experimental parameters.

For the DBF dimer, only b-type transitions were observed (Figure 1c, Table 2). Four DBF dimer structures (shown in Figure S4) were calculated with relative energies within 3 kJ/mol (B3LYP-D3(BJ)/def2TZVP). All four are formed via π - π intermolecular interactions but differ in the relative orientation of the two planar DBF molecules within the complex. These different relative orientations cause only small changes in the mass distribution because of the overall large mass of the dimer ($C_{24}O_2H_{16}$, molecular mass 336 amu). Thus, the rotational constants for the four calculated dimer structures are clearly similar (Table 2), which complicates an assignment only based on rotational constants. However, the fact that we only observed b-type transitions gives useful structural information. The monomer dipole moments along the C_2 symmetry axis have different relative arrangements in the calculated dimer structures, as indicated by arrows in Figure S4. This gives rise to characteristic differences in the electric charge distribution and thus in the electric dipole-moment components μ_a , μ_b , and μ_c (Table 2). The observation of only b-type transitions supports the assignment of the experimental structure as Dimer 1, which is also the global minimum. For Dimers 2 and 3, the μ_b dipole-moment components are predicted to be identical or close to zero so that we expect no b-type transitions. For Dimer 4, we would expect some additional (weak) a- and c-type transitions, which were not observed.

The assignment of the experimentally observed DBF dimer as Dimer 1 is also supported by the good agreement between the experimental and calculated A rotational constant as well as by comparing the difference between the rotational constants, B-C, of 37.4 MHz. By taking all of this into account, we have sufficient evidence to assign the experimentally observed DBF dimer structure to the calculated lowest-energy isomer Dimer 1. This structure is characterized by an interesting symmetry. Based on inspection, this symmetry seems to arise from the interplay between attractive π - π interactions on the one hand and repulsion between the oxygen lone pairs and the π cloud on the other hand. Note that the two DBF monomers are not arranged

perfectly parallel but deviated by about 12 degrees (see Figure S5), which supports this interpretation.

This is different to the DPE dimer where the ether oxygen atom is involved in an attractive (CH-O) interaction, which is supported by the flexible structure of DPE. For the DBF dimer, CH-O interactions are not possible in a stacked arrangement because of DBF's planarity.

Table 2. Comparison of experimental and calculated molecular parameters of the DBF dimer. The experimental values are obtained from a fit to an asymmetric rotor Hamiltonian using the SPFIT software. The calculations were performed at the B3LYP-D3(BJ)/def2TZVP level of theory.

Parameters	Experiment	Calc. (Dimer 1)	Calc. (Dimer 2)	Calc. (Dimer 3)	Calc. (Dimer 4)
A (MHz)	300.90323(17)	303	359	334	313
B (MHz)	227.98085(17)	232	220	230	230
C (MHz)	190.60573(17)	192	190	201	192
B-C (MHz)	37.4	40	30	29	38
Δ_J (kHz)	0.0199(11)				
Δ_{JK} (kHz)	0.0180(18)				
ΔE (kJ/mol)		0	1.2	2.0	2.9
$\mu_a \mu_b \mu_c$ (D)		0 0.6 0	0.3 0.1 0.1	0 0 1.2	0.5 0.7 0.6
σ (kHz)	6.09				
$N_{lines}^{[b]}$ (a b c)	83 (0 83 0)				

^[a] A, B, and C are the rotational constants, Δ_J and Δ_{JK} are the experimental centrifugal distortion constants, and σ is the standard deviation of the fit.

^[b] Total number of rotational transitions included in the fit.

Figure 2. Optimized structures (B3LYP-D3(BJ)/def2-TZVP) of (a) DPE, (b) DBF, and (c) FLU dimers. Top row: side view, bottom row: top view. In the top view, the bottom molecule is made transparent for better visibility and differentiation between the two moieties. Ray's asymmetry parameter κ (see text) is also included.

Despite the already mentioned differences between the DPE and the DBF dimer structures, they also show similarities (Figure 2). The positions and relative arrangements of the oxygen atoms are strikingly similar in both dimers, while we observe a transition from CH- π to π - π bonding once the binding partners become planar and rigid. The distances between the two oxygen atoms in the dimers are quite comparable with 5.2 Å for DPE vs. 5.4 Å for DBF, based on the quantum-chemical calculations.

Table 3. Comparison of experimental and calculated molecular parameters of the FLU dimer. The experimental values are ascertained from a fit to an asymmetric rotor Hamiltonian using the SPFIT software. The calculations were performed at the B3LYP-D3(BJ)/def2TZVP level of theory.

Parameters	Experiment	Calc. (Dimer 1)	Calc. (Dimer 2)
A (MHz)	260.86916(27)	266	324
B (MHz)	242.82643(10)	245	240
C (MHz)	215.586530(98)	219	176
Δ_J (kHz)	0.00702(20)		
Δ_K (kHz)	0.00639(36)		
ΔE (kJ/mol)		0	5.5
$\mu_a \mu_b \mu_c$ (D)		0.5 0 0	0 0 0
σ (kHz)	4.47		
$N_{lines}^{[b]}$ (a b c)		116 (116 0 0)	

^[a] A, B, and C are the rotational constants, Δ_J and Δ_K are the experimental centrifugal distortion constants, and σ is the standard deviation of the fit.

^[b] Total number of rotational transitions included in the fit.

The FLU dimer ($C_{26}H_{20}$, molecular mass 332 amu) completes the series. The experimentally observed dimer structure is

shown in Figure 2c, with the rotational parameters being reported in Table 3. It is strongly related to the structure of the DBF dimer. The FLU dimer is stacked, with the two monomers being skewed with respect to one another by approximately 90 degrees, showing mainly two types of interaction when inspecting the structures: two CH- π interactions involving the CH_2 groups as well as parallel-displaced π - π interaction between the aromatic rings. Different to the DBF dimer, this FLU dimer structure is almost perfectly parallel, with an angle between the two monomer planes of only 0.7 degrees (Figure S5). A non-polar, second dimer where the two monomers are stacked but with their long axes aligned is about 5.5 kJ/mol higher in energy than the experimentally confirmed structure (Figure S6). A T-shaped moiety, similar to the global minimum of the benzene dimer and consisting of CH- π contacts, is about 22 kJ/mol higher in energy.

It is now interesting to compare the results for the three dimers with respect to a) their structures and b) their binding energies. Ray's asymmetry parameter $\kappa = \frac{2B-A-C}{A-C}$ provides a measure of the asymmetry of the complexes. It ranges from -1 in the prolate to +1 in the oblate case. $\kappa=0$ corresponds to the fully asymmetric structure. According to these, the DPE dimer is a near prolate asymmetric top ($\kappa=-0.75$) while the DBF dimer is significantly more asymmetric with $\kappa=-0.32$. The FLU dimer has a positive κ value ($\kappa=+0.2$) and thus is closer to an oblate top, but still quite asymmetric.

The binding energies, calculated at the B3LYP-D3(BJ)/def2-TZVP level and corrected for basis set superposition errors (BSSE), as well as results of symmetry adapted perturbation theory (SAPT) calculations,^[12] which give a qualitative breakdown of the individual contributions to the binding energy, are summarized in Table 4. The binding energies of DPE and DBF are comparable (-41.2 vs. -42.3 kJ/mol), while FLU is more strongly bound (-51.1 kJ/mol). This might be surprising at first glance because, naively, one would expect stronger interactions for the molecules containing the hetero atom or/and the stronger

dipole moment (DPE). SAPT(0)/jun-cc-pVDZ calculations together with revisiting the structures can help to glean better insight into these binding energies (Table 4). E_{tot} corresponds to the binding energy from the SAPT(0)/jun-cc-pVDZ calculations (only based on the interaction energies), which shows a similar trend as E_{b} . The three dimers have significant dispersion contributions accounting for 60-70% of the overall attractive interaction. For the electrostatic contribution, the DPE dimer dominates, which probably arises from its larger dipole moment and from the attractive CH-O interactions between the two molecules in the DPE dimer (vide supra). Furthermore, contributions from induction are small and on the same order of magnitude for all three dimers. This can be expected for such stacked structures because of the rather small polarizability of these molecules in the direction perpendicular to the aromatic plane. As expected, the contribution is somewhat larger for the DPE dimer because of the non-planarity of the DPE monomer.

Another way to visualize the different parts of intermolecular interactions is by using non-covalent interaction (NCI) plots (Figure S7).^[13] NCI plots are a visualization index based on the density and its derivatives, and they enable identification of non-covalent interactions. In contrast to the DPE dimer, the planar structures of both DBF and FLU allow for good molecular overlap. In the FLU dimer all three rings are involved in the attractive interaction via π - π and CH- π contacts. In the DBF dimer, however, a compromise has to be found to minimize repulsion between the oxygen lone pairs and the π cloud of the phenyl rings. The almost perfect parallel stacking in the FLU dimer might also contribute to its larger binding energy compared to the DPE and the DBF dimers.

Table 4. Results of SAPT(0)/jun-cc-pVDZ calculations for the three optimized dimers. The binding energy, E_{b} , calculated at the B3LYP-D3(BJ)/def2-TZVP level of theory is also given for comparison as well as the respective relative contributions to the overall attractive interactions ($E_{\text{el}}+E_{\text{ind}}+E_{\text{disp}}$).^[b]

Dimer	E_{b} ^[a]	E_{tot}	$E_{\text{el}}^{(1)}$	$E_{\text{disp}}^{(1)}$	$E_{\text{ind}}^{(1)}$	$E_{\text{exch}}^{(1)}$
DPE ₂	-41.2	-45.8	-35.3 (30.4%)	-71.8 (61.8%)	-9.0 (7.8%)	70.3
DBF ₂	-42.3	-51.5	-29.5 (26.5%)	-80.9 (72.8%)	-6.7 (6.0%)	65.6
FLU ₂	-51.1	-60.0	-33.7 (24.8%)	-93.3 (68.6%)	-9.0 (6.6%)	76.2

^[a] binding energy (B3LYP-D3(BJ)/def2-TZVP), BSSE corrected.

^[b] Negative values indicate an attractive contribution to the overall energy E_{tot} , while positive values are repulsive contributions to E_{tot} .

In summary, all three dimers show striking structural similarities, although governed by different intermolecular interactions. The DPE dimer consists of two structurally flexible DPE units, where the internal dynamics of the DPE monomers are locked. Its structure is governed by CH- π as well as additional CH-O interactions that further stabilize the dimer. The rigid DBF dimer has mainly π - π interactions where the two monomers are skewed with respect to one another to facilitate an optimal contact and minimize electrostatic repulsion between the π -clouds and the oxygen atom lone pairs. The two DBF molecules are not fully parallel but deviate by about 12 degrees. The dimer of FLU is dominated by π - π and CH- π interactions involving the non-aromatic hydrogen atoms, with all three rings being involved

in the intermolecular contact and an almost perfect parallel arrangement.

Our systematic study of these structurally related aromatic molecules shows the differences and similarities upon dimer formation and the kind of interactions that control their aggregation. We found that a subtle balance of forces is the main contributor to the observed geometries. The results presented here will help chemists to better understand the factors at play in the first stages of molecular aggregation, which can be relevant for soot production in combustion as well as grain formation in astrochemical environments.

Acknowledgements

This work was financially supported by the Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (SCHN1280/4 - 2, project number 271359857; SU121/5 - 2, project number 271107160) in the context of the priority program SPP 1807 "Control of London dispersion interactions in molecular chemistry". We acknowledge the use of the GWDG computer cluster and thank Sérgio R. Domingos for his help with the NCI plots. M. F. acknowledges support from the Hamburg International Max Planck Research School UFAST, and A.L.S. is supported via the Louise Johnson Fellowship.

Keywords: non-covalent interactions • rotational spectroscopy • dispersion • molecular complexes • aromatic dimers

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